

Skills 4 EOSC

Workshop on open science, research data management and decision-making Report

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Abstract

The goal of the Brainstorming Workshop was to promote an open discussion among scientists and different stakeholders on Open Science (OS) and Research Data Management (RDM), exchanging and sharing visions, perspectives and opinions on data sharing and management with a particular focus on policy making and decision making focusing in particular on Disaster Risk Management (DRM) in the Civil Protection area.

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DELIVERY SLIP

	<i>DATE</i>	<i>NAME</i>	<i>PARTNER/ACTIVITY</i>	<i>DATE</i>
FROM:		Mario Locati	INGV	15.04.2024
		Sara Di Giorgio	GARR and Skills4EOSC	05.04.2024
		Giovanna Forlenza	INGV and ARISTOTLE	05.04.2024
MODERATED BY:		Massimo Cocco	INGV and EPOS	05.04.2024
REVIEWED BY:		Daniela Di Bucci	ICDP	24.05.2024
APPROVED BY:		Emma Lazzeri	CNR	28.05.2024

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1. Executive summary

The Brainstorming Workshop on Open Science, Research Data Management, and Decision-Making was organised online on the 9th of April, 2024, as a joint effort by Skills4EOSC, EPOS, INGV and the Italian Civil Protection. The Workshop aimed to foster open discussion on Open Science (OS) and Research Data Management (RDM) among scientists and stakeholders involved in Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Civil Protection. The workshop discussed various European Union (EU) initiatives promoting OS and RDM related to the European Data Strategy and the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM), as well as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction.

The participants discussed various key concepts, including the Pan-European framework of OS and RDM, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Research Infrastructures, and Evidence-based Decision Making at pan-European and national levels with particular emphasis on open data and open access from a civil protection perspective.

The workshop identified several challenges and gaps in OS and RDM practices in the DRM context:

- Finding common ground among diverse stakeholders about Open Science terminology
- Defining roles, professional profiles, competencies, and responsibilities
- Managing the data life cycle and taxonomy
- Communicating uncertainties associated with data
- Ensuring data and knowledge usability for decision-making
- Balancing openness with data privacy and security concerns

To address these challenges, the participants identified several needs and opportunities for the future development of OS and RDM in DRM. These included:

- Promoting a shared cultural framework among stakeholders
- Developing standardised procedures for data management and sharing
- Establishing clear definitions of roles and responsibilities
- Investing in training and capacity building
- Fostering collaboration between scientists and decision-makers

The workshop concluded that OS and RDM play a crucial role in strengthening evidence-based decision-making in DRM. By addressing the challenges and embracing the opportunities identified, stakeholders can improve data sharing, collaboration, and the use of scientific knowledge to enhance disaster risk prevention, preparedness and response.

2. Goals of the workshop

The goal of the Brainstorming Workshop was to promote an open discussion among scientists and different stakeholders on Open Science (OS) and Research Data Management (RDM), exchanging and sharing visions, perspectives and opinions on data sharing and management with a particular focus on policy making and decision making focusing in particular on Disaster Risk Management (DRM) in the Civil Protection area.

3. Reference frameworks

Before any consideration, it is worth mentioning that a series of regulations are in place in the European Union:

3.1. European Data Strategy

To put the [Digital Single Market](#) and the [Digital Single Market Strategy](#) into practice, the European Union (EU) is progressively adopting regulations for implementing its [Data Strategy](#) that involves the promotion of “*data dissemination as a catalyst for economic growth*”. Especially for data generated using public funding, the EU tries to facilitate anyone interested in data to be able to access and use it, without restrictions. The most relevant and recent regulation is the following: the [Commission Recommendation \(EU\) 2018/790](#) of 25 April 2018 on **access to and preservation of scientific information**, the [Directive \(EU\) 2019/1024](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on **open data and the re-use of public sector information**, the [Regulation \(EU\) 2022/868](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (**Data Governance Act**), the [Commission Implementing Regulation \(EU\) 2023/138](#) of 21 December 2022 laying down a list of specific **high-value datasets** and the arrangements for their publication and re-use, and finally, the [Regulation \(EU\) 2023/2854](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (**Data Act**).

3.2. European and international DRM policies

Past and recent natural disasters, often transboundary and multi-scale in time and space, have demonstrated how people and societies have become more exposed and vulnerable to natural and man-made hazards highlighting the limits of the current disaster response system as well the need to strengthen Europe’s ability to prevent and prepare for emergencies. To this effect, the [Union Civil Protection Mechanism \(UCPM\) 1313/2013](#)¹ has been established to strengthen the cooperation between the EU, the Member States (MS), and Participant States (PS) to

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32013D1313>

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facilitate coordination in the field of civil protection. The European Response Coordination Centre ([ERCC](#)), operating within the Directorate-General for Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection (DG-ECHO), is the 24/7 operational hub of the Mechanism. Due to its mandate, the ERCC requires a strong analytical capacity and knowledge base to provide timely, relevant and reliable information as part of a comprehensive emergency preparedness strategy. More formally, the EU legislation has been adjourned with ERCC that “shall have access to operational, analytical, monitoring, information management and communication capabilities to address a broad range of emergencies within and outside the Union” (cf. Parliament, 2021).

Recently, the UCPM has been [amended](#)² to strengthen European response and DRM capacity by increasing the availability and use of scientific knowledge on disasters to facilitate a rapid and efficient emergency response and decision-making process in the event of disasters or imminent disasters (Article 3 (e) Decision No 1313/2013/EU) through more rapid and more accurate Early Warning Systems (Article. 8 (c) of Decision No 1313/2013/EU) as well as to improve the knowledge base on DRM and facilitate the sharing of knowledge and the results of scientific research. The latter will be implemented through the [Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network](#)³.

In February 2023, according to Article 6(5) of the UCPM legislation, the EC adopted the Disaster Resilience Goals⁴ to strengthen the EU’s collective capacity to withstand the impacts of future disasters, and protect citizens, livelihoods and the environment. These goals are i) Anticipate, ii) Prepare, iii) Alert, iv) Respond, and v) Secure. In all these goals, scientific knowledge is called to complement MS capacity at national and societal levels to deal with hazards.

At the international level, the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) 2015-2030 outlines four priorities for action to prevent new and reduce existing disaster risks. At the onset of adopting the Sendai Framework, the Information and Knowledge Management for Disaster Risk Reduction (IKM4DRR) community found that special attention was needed to generate and sustain information and knowledge at all levels to make informed decision-making and progress toward the goals of the Sendai Framework.

4. Stakeholders

Open Data (OD) and OS do not only concern research. Their concept and motivation embrace a wide range of stakeholders spanning from the OD and OS practitioners to their end-users. This is particularly evident in the field of DRR and DRM to mainstream prevention and preparedness actions and promote a more coordinated and coherent response to natural and/or man-made disasters across policy decision-makers and society. There are different ways

² https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-8-2019-0070_EN.html?redirect#BKMD-9

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32021D1956>

⁴ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2023.056.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2023%3A056%3AFULL

to categorise stakeholders with an unlike level of contribution and engagement in OS, RDM, and the decision-making process. The most common classification is grouped into three large blocks, namely i) science, ii) policy and decision-makers, and iii) society. Beyond this general classification, further sub-grouping can be applied as follows.

Science	
	<p>Publicly funded Research Performing Organisations (RPO) Any University or any other form of organisation that has Research as an objective and that is officially recognised as a legal entity is entitled to receive public funding to perform research activities.</p>
	<p>Data producers Scientists contribute to OD by sharing and communicating their research via open access and to OS through their research and European and national scientific initiatives such as INSPIRE the Copernicus Emergency Management System and the Global Disaster Alerting Coordination System (GDACS).</p>
	<p>Federated Data and Research Infrastructures European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where researchers, innovators, companies and citizens can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. On the other hand, Research Infrastructures (RI) are facilities that provide resources and services for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. These include major equipment or sets of instruments, knowledge-related facilities such as collections, archives or research data infrastructures, computing systems, and communication networks⁵. One example is the European Plate Observing System (EPOS).</p>
	<p>Knowledge broker Any private or public organisation (eg. RPO), a group of people or a single person bringing together interdisciplinary expertise that is appointed to holistically frame policy needs and develop evidence-based information and knowledge by organising and making accessible OD and OS. As an example, the European Commission (EC)'s Joint Research Centre (JRC) carries out research in various fields to provide independent advice to European policymakers and translate science into policies. To bring together scientific and knowledge expertise, new tools have been created by the EC following the endorsements of the concept of "Knowledge Centers" in its Communication on Data, Information and Knowledge Management⁶:</p>

⁵ Definition taken from European Research Infrastructures, European Commission: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures_en

⁶ C(2016) 6626 final.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC) supports the translation of complex scientific outcomes into usable information and provides science-based advice for DRM policies. Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network (UCPKN) acts as an innovation catalyst in civil protection and DRM by stimulating research, new technologies and processes. DRMKC is leading its Science Pillar which is a major step in the science-policy interface in the DRM domain.
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	<p>Service providers</p> <p>Scientific organisations and European scientific partnerships, are formally mandated to provide advice and services for disaster risks to the national Civil Protection authority, providing decision-makers with authoritative scientific expert advice based on shareable OD and OS frameworks. Examples of such European scientific partnership initiatives are ARISTOTLE-eENHSP “European Natural Hazard Scientific Partnership” and the European Anthropogenic Hazard Partnership Programme (EAHSP).</p>
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Policy and decision-makers at the national and European levels

	<p>Civil Protection Authorities at national and sub-national Level</p> <p>Multi-level operational structure with a legal mandate to operate at the national and sub-national level in the area of civil protection; they produce and manage data by promoting OS in close cooperation with scientific communities.</p>
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	<p>Emergency Response Coordination Centre</p> <p>The ERCC acts by law⁷ as a deployment hub between all EU MS, PS, the affected country and civil protection and humanitarian experts, coordinating the delivery of assistance to disaster-stricken countries within the UCPM. ERCC translates scientific knowledge into broader options for their emergency management mandate within the UCPM.</p>
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Society

	<p>Industry</p> <p>The industry comprises the private sector, particularly impacted by natural and man-made hazards.</p>
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	<p>Civil society</p> <p>Citizens are often involved in actions and initiatives referred to as “<i>citizen science</i>”.</p>
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⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/836 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 amending Decision No 1313/2013/EU on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism

5. Summary of the workshop

5.1. The Pan-European framework of OS and RDM, EOSC - *Volker Beckmann*

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) represents the Pan-European framework for OS and RDM. EOSC was created to align with the EC's goal of building a unified digital infrastructure that supports research and innovation across Europe. It's designed to foster cross-domain data sharing and collaboration among stakeholders, including the private sector, and is envisioned as “the European contribution to establishing a web of FAIR data”.

Four main dimensions define EOSC:

1. **Governance:** EOSC operates with a structured governance model that brings together the EC, MS, and the EOSC Association to guide collaborative efforts.
2. **Funding:** EOSC's funding comes from a Co-programmed Partnership involving the EC, the EOSC Association (representing users and providers), and MS contributions via the EOSC Steering Board.
3. **Policies:** Member States support EOSC by formulating and implementing policies that adhere to OS principles, funding Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) to join EOSC, and providing in-kind contributions and services.
4. **The EOSC Federation:** EOSC is more than just an infrastructure—it is a federation, a community, and a process that facilitates collaboration among a wide array of stakeholders and builds on existing research infrastructures and services.

EOSC aims to promote an “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” approach, encouraging Open and FAIR practices while respecting legal boundaries. This approach is embedded in project planning, with OS training included in the curriculum to promote an Open and FAIR-by-design philosophy. However, the responsibility for managing sensitive or non-open data lies with the respective research domain infrastructures.

The **concept of Nodes** within EOSC is still evolving, with discussions focusing on their structure and criteria. The goal is to create a network that supports interoperability, resource sharing, and knowledge exchange among MS and institutions.

5.2. Research Infrastructures: Open access to Data and RDM, EPOS ERIC - *M. Cocco*

Research Infrastructures (RI) play a key role in data generation and integration, data that is often of great use in many decision-making activities. A RI is a well-structured and governed effort aiming at providing resources and services for the research communities to conduct

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research and foster innovation in their fields. The goal requires the coordination of various types of scientific facilities, 1) generating data, 2) collecting and storing data, 3) analysing data, and 4) providing access to data.

European RI such as EPOS ERIC adopt a federated approach, where the overarching governing boards are composed of representatives of distinct scientific communities and cover many different profiles. The common goal is to make authoritative and quality-controlled data available. The goal is achieved by adopting shared and internationally-recognized interoperability standards, from both a data policy and technological point-of-view. The adoption of these shared standards put the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) into practice.

EPOS ERIC provides a robust infrastructure to achieve coherent access to data that is otherwise restricted to very specific scientific communities, an effective solution to reduce the so-called “disciplinary silos”.

Anyone involved in daily research activities is aware that researchers are rarely inclined to plan and adopt data management strategies covering the entire data life cycle. Instead, they are much more inclined to spend their time performing cutting-edge science and publishing papers because their careers depend on them. By participating in the activities of a RI, each scientific community is therefore challenged to adopt better and more formalised research data management strategies, providing access to their data without any service interruption by developing reliable and efficient data infrastructure. In addition, they are encouraged to adopt formalised quality control procedures to avoid publishing potentially unreliable data. The challenge in this environment is the acquisition of the required competencies because these scientific communities find it difficult to attract these highly skilled profiles.

5.3. Evidence-based Decision Making: pan-European context, DG-ECHO-KN - *G. Vivo*

Launched in December 2021, the Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network (UCP KN) is one of the tools of the UCPM to i) support capacity-building programmes among civil protection and DRM stakeholders and ii) create a bridge between the scientific community and operational stakeholders to promote evidence-based decision making in DRM. To achieve these objectives, the UCP KN has set up two pillars, respectively: i) the Capacity Development pillar and ii) the Science pillar. These pillars sustain the UCP KN mission by bringing together Disaster Risk Managers and Civil Protection Authorities (networking), making more actionable and usable information available to decision-makers and practitioners in DRM, and fostering innovation in the DRM area through research programmes.

The UCP KN provides space and tools to sustain OA; most of them are still under development (among the others, soon the launch of a library that will be populated with publications, manuals, reports etc) but several challenges have been already identified such as how to

communicate data limitation, shortcoming and loss data not yet captured to policy-makers in prevention phase, how to shape more robust ways to link science and policy with clear commitments, how to support similar discussion/brainstorming for DRM, and the need to standardise OS to meet gaps in DRM.

5.4. National Civil Protection Agency: open access and decision making, ICPD - *D. Di Bucci*

The Italian Civil Protection Authority (CPA) is a complex system covering the entire DRM cycle provided for by specific law⁸. It has responsibilities in a wide range of fields and its components are multi-level distinguished into national, regional and local components, operational structures (including the scientific community), and contributing subjects. In Italy, the relationship between Science and Civil Protection is established by law⁹ to, on one side, formally recognise the important role the scientific community plays in civil protection activities and, on the other hand, it expresses the need to better regulate the role of the various actors involved in the civil protection system. It should be noted that the Science-Civil Protection relationship played by the law is not only formal but it shapes this collaboration in a very practical way because all the contributions are managed according to the Civil Protection Code. Some examples of this cooperation are a) routine and operational activities for DRM, b) experimental activities preparatory to a), c) target research and products for risk management, d) collaboration in the preparation of technical regulations of interest. Key components of such a Science-Civil Protection relationship are the Competence Centers as those entities that provide services, information, data, processing and technical-scientific contributions in specific fields. In this context, special emphasis is placed on establishing networks of Competence Centres for the development of integrated topics and in a multi-risk approach (such as the Consorzio Italiano per la Ricerca sulla Riduzione dei Rischi-[CI3R](#)).

Data is produced and managed by the scientific community in close collaboration with the CPA. CPA collects, uses, manages and disseminates scientific data in different ways as prescribed by law and intrinsic practice.

6. Open topics for further discussion

6.1. Finding common ground among diverse stakeholders about Open Science terminology

Open Science and Open Access to research data require data management and the governance of this process involving the whole data lifecycle. In this framework, the sharing of scientific

⁸ Legislative Decree No. 1 of January 2, 2018

⁹ Law No. 225 of 1992

information concerns the communication of the contents, the use and the application of research data to progress in science and innovation for science for society. Making scientific information available to stakeholders and society at large is an essential step to improve the understanding of scientific methods, scientific products and their use and application to evidence-based decision-making. This is a key contribution to improve the literacy of citizens and stakeholders on the use of scientific data. Evidence-based decision-making involves experts providing expertise to interpret scientific evidence and outcomes as well as their knowledge to feed decision and policy making. This is especially evident in DRM where decisions are taken based on timely and reliable scientific knowledge. Exploiting the impact of OS and OA on research data for evidence-based decision-making requires a full understanding of this complex and multi-process framework as well as awareness of the necessary resources, roles and responsibilities. A clear example is offered by interdisciplinary and multi-hazard scientific networking where challenges are various spanning from the need to build common languages among different scientific disciplines producing aggregated outputs to sharing specific knowledge among stakeholders that may have different roles, mandates, and responsibilities. In this regard, scientists, data providers and decision-makers require further opportunities for a dialogue in a lessons-learned mode to better identify gaps and needs and address them through clearer governance frameworks, shared roadmaps and more sustainable financial programmes with continuous balance to mutually build trust and consensus.

6.2. Definition of the roles, professional profiles, competencies and responsibilities

The complex chain starting from data generation up to decision making involves different processes governed by different stakeholders with different roles, professional profiles and competencies affiliated to any stakeholder committed to govern RDM and information provision for decision making. The recognition of these different roles and expertise is essential to create awareness and foster progress in RDM, OA and decision-making. This requires the sharing of common definitions of roles as well as the shared recognition of responsibilities.

The common goal of achieving evidence-based decision-making highlights the need for common European-level procedures for data management, pointing out the lack of a standardised approach to harmonise institutional policies. This is the main task of pan-European Research Infrastructures, such as those included in the ESFRI (European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures) Roadmap that includes EPOS. This underlines the challenge of defining roles, acquiring the necessary competencies, and establishing a framework that promotes data interoperability, ultimately supporting open science and evidence-based decision-making.

The EU project Skills4EOSC is working in this direction, mapping career profiles related to OS practices and defining, through co-creation, the “Minimum Viable Skillset” (MVS) for different EOSC actors and OS practitioners, including researchers, data stewards, knowledge brokers,

policymakers, and other stakeholders. This effort creates a shared framework for recognizing competencies and setting up specific training programs with the goal of making 'Open Science as the new normal'.

6.3. Data Life Cycle, Research Data Management, shared data taxonomy

The experience coming from the scientific communities involved in EPOS fully exemplifies the complexity of the RDM process, especially when it comes to providing scientific data as a service to stakeholders outside the scientific communities involved in data generation. The scientific community is represented by scientists, data providers and managers working in research organisations committed to generate, curate and share scientific data and services. They possess the required expertise to assess the quality of collected data and exploit their impact on science and society. However, the term data concerns different digital objects spanning, from raw data to community-shared scientific products and software. A clear data taxonomy is key, and a classification based on 4 levels of intellectual contribution and scientific complexity is suggested by EPOS. Level 0 stands for "Raw data", data that represent the output of the sensors or actuators used to measure the physical properties or phenomena and collect observations. Level 1) "Data product" coming from nearly automated procedures applied to raw data. Level 2) "Data product", which results from scientists' investigations, data that requires the intervention of scientists to interpret and add values to Level 0 or Level 1 data. Finally, at Level 3) "Integrated Data product" coming from complex analyses or community-shared products, which require collaborative processes over a considerable time span. Software and services should be included in this taxonomy.

Not considering all data equal, allows us to adopt suitable data policies and access rules necessary to govern the RDM process, and sustain OS taking into account technical, legal and ethical aspects such as intellectual property rights and licensing. It appears clear that effective governance of RDM is necessary, especially because making scientific data accessible to multiple stakeholders requires addressing these issues making the sharing of data sustainable.

6.4. Preserving and communicating quality and uncertainty associated with data

The quality of data should emerge rather than excellence, as the more reliable and authoritative data is available, the better chance decision-makers are provided with a solid basis on which they can make decisions.

Whenever possible, quality data should be associated with uncertainty in its estimation; uncertainty is an expression of the way data was generated and a measure of its reliability. Being able to interpret and use such uncertainty correctly requires scientific knowledge, that is why the scientific community should be involved when data is used, and why researchers should try their best to effectively communicate it, adopting a suitable vocabulary shared by the target community.

6.5. Ensuring data and knowledge usability for a more efficient decision-making process

Ensuring data and knowledge are useful, usable and used in DRR and DRM is a great opportunity for scientists and stakeholders to find a commanding ground to translate data, scientific information and evidence into knowledge and practice in a timely, accessible and policy-relevant manner. These elements are different in value according to the DRM chain. For example, in the prevention and recovery phases of the risk cycle, it is important to ensure data interoperability while, convergently, in preparedness and response phases timely and reliable scientific and expert knowledge may impact rapid and immediate actions in emergencies. This implies the recognition, on the other end, of the authoritative role of research organisations and scientists committed to providing knowledge and supporting decision-making and, on the other hand, of decision-makers and their extensive expertise in DRM as a whole. This in turn leads to mutual trust and social acceptance.

Closer collaboration and dialogue among scientists and stakeholders must be ensured, from one side, to meet stakeholders' needs to guarantee capacity-building to access OD and OS and effectively use and re-use them and, from the other side, to facilitate mutual and peer exchange of perspectives and knowledge in a lesson learnt approach.

6.6. As open as possible, as closed as necessary

In the pursuit of making informed and responsible decisions, processes are conducted within the framework of precise legal constraints that prioritise privacy and adherence to established laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which serves as safeguards against the indiscriminate sharing of sensitive information and emphasise the duty to uphold privacy rights. Furthermore, by legal mandates, scientific information utilised by Civil Protection must meet stringent criteria of maturity and recognition within the scientific community, ensuring reliance on robust and credible data sources and research results.

Transparency is integral to decision-making processes, emphasising accountability and fostering trust among stakeholders and society in general. Experts supporting decision-making are encouraged to share their data openly or with qualified peers to facilitate peer review and ensure the authoritative basis of decisions. This commitment to transparency not only upholds academic rigour but also enhances the reliability and comprehensiveness of deliberations.

Decisions are grounded in evidence-based practices, rejecting the concept of "black boxes" in favour of open discourse and accountability. While immediate transparency may not always be feasible, for instance during some emergencies, the commitment remains steadfast in providing clarity as soon as possible to elucidate the reasoning and considerations that inform decisions. This approach ensures that society remains informed, confident, and engaged in decision-making processes that impact collective well-being.

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By maintaining a balance between openness and privacy, efforts are directed towards cultivating an environment of trust and accountability in decision-making, anchored in legal compliance, scientific rigour, and a commitment to transparency. Nevertheless, openness is the first step in the co-creation process, one of the main pillars of Open Science, making sure all stakeholders are involved in the design of relevant research and evidence-informed decision-making processes. This commitment reflects the ethos encapsulated in the title "As Open as Possible, As Closed as Necessary," emphasising the importance of balancing transparency with the need to protect sensitive information and privacy rights. Through these endeavours, the aim is to not only navigate challenges effectively but also to promote public confidence and understanding of processes and outcomes.

6.7. Required change in the Research output evaluation (COARA) and careers associated with Open Science

COARA (COalition for Advancing Research Assessment) is a global initiative aimed at improving the evaluation of research outputs and academic careers in the context of Open Science, an occasion the move away from the "publish or perish". COARA promotes FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and more transparent methods, shifting focus from quantitative metrics to a broader range of research activities like data sharing, open-source software, and social impact. To drive change, a consistent adoption at the institutional level is crucial to ensure these new practices are implemented effectively and a shared approach among Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) is key, incorporating COARA's principles into institutional policies.

6.8. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

Modern machine learning applications require a large amount of good and reliable data for training their algorithms, such as Large Language Models. These models benefit enormously from the availability of openly accessible data, even better if such data is accessible in a machine-friendly way. Research Infrastructures are a perfect resource for machine learning, as they conveniently provide large quantities of authoritative scientific data using standard services. In turn, algorithms should be open and transparent. These two conditions on data and algorithms enable true evidence-based decision-making.

Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence already play an important role both in the scientific communities and in the decision-making field, for example, to reduce information overload to a manageable factor. In the future, their use and importance will surely further increase and all stakeholders agree on the need for dedicated discussions.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning will also contribute to creating a wealth of scientific products from users of data and research infrastructures. While this is important for progress in science, it also opens ethical and governance issues since these new data products must be

quality controlled and provided respecting existing protocols and authoritatively established procedures for decision making.

7. Gaps and needs

7.1. Exploring data granularity gaps and needs for society

The level of granularity related to the extent and degree of openness of scientific data and information to society is a highly sensitive element of the OS policy since it may affect:

- on one hand, the efficiency of the decision-making process toward society (top-down approach), and
- on the other one, the understanding and acceptance of disseminated information from society.

The level of granularity is set by specific needs based on which the amount of data is collected, stored, and analysed; this means that the highest level of granularity (more detailed data) results in a more comprehensive understanding while, conversely, the lowest one reduces the capacity to analyse in-depth the subject matter but, at the same time, allow society to have them in a very catchy manner. To allow a fairer and more open shift of science toward society, OS policy would need to increase the transparency of various aspects of their work, starting from the research to the dissemination of the final products, by also ensuring a cooperative engagement of societal stakeholders to identify specific needs and gaps that science should address through collaborative tools (bottom-up approach).

The granularity of data can be modulated to better strengthen awareness and capacity to understand the scientific approach to hazards and risk, a way to provide scientific information in an integrated and suitable way (lay-language and accessible information) to society for strengthening awareness and capacity to understand.

How scientific information feeds knowledge also depends on trust, societal acceptance and recognition of the authoritative role of scientists and stakeholders involved in decision-making. A further element to be considered in discussing the granularity and openness of research data concerns the distinction between mid- to long-term actions performed during “ordinary times” and short-term actions done during emergencies and crises caused by events with high impact on society.

7.2. Conflict management as part of integrated decision-making processes

Potential conflicts in the access of Open Data and OS may occur in integrated decision-making processes since this process entails a large number of stakeholders with different interests, roles, mandates and responsibilities. This is particularly evident in DRM, for instance in

transboundary and multi-hazard and multi-risk preparedness and response actions. In most cases, the access to data, scientific information, and knowledge is shared without corresponding access to OS such as work frameworks, standard operational protocols or tools. Hence, the application of scientific knowledge may appear an automatic element to be used not in an integrated manner. It is also worth mentioning that it would be of great importance to clarify the definition of authoritative mandate (authorised by law) and endorsement to carry out certain activities or services (not legally bound), complementary or not to the decision-making processes. This will represent an opportunity for the stakeholders to create a truly complementary chain of knowledge. Thus, stakeholders would need to resolve such potential conflict(s) in a more participatory manner by creating more opportunities for dialogue, exchange of experience, and access to OS in lessons learnt mode.

7.3. Building a shared cultural framework among stakeholders dealing with Open Science

One of the biggest challenges ahead that each Research Infrastructure is facing is related to long-term sustainability and keeping the scientific community involved. The adoption of a good Open Science practice requires long-term scientific, technological and political decisions, therefore forcing multiple profiles to work together to design viable solutions. In addition, keeping multiple stakeholders involved requires being able to efficiently and clearly communicate the scientific outcomes, its added value and limits. The scientific community is more or less accustomed to assessing the reliability of the shared data, whereas it is much less accustomed to dealing with the potential use -or misuse- of the data once it is made publicly accessible.

The desired shared cultural framework should also consider a full recognition of the resources (technological, human and financial) necessary to govern FAIR RDM, sustain OS and support decision-making. This should include the accountability and traceability of data providers (to keep them motivated to share high-quality data) and research organisations (key actors in ensuring the sustainability of RDM governance) as well as the associated ethical issues emerging when open access to data deals with DRM, risk communication and safe and sustainable use of georesources.

Further discussion among all stakeholders is required to build a common ground. It is of fundamental importance to mutually define the roles, competencies and potential contribution of each party, in the view of contributing to a more efficient, consistent, and robust policy and decision-making process.

Disclaimer

This document is the result of a joint work done by a heterogeneous group of rapporteurs with specific and diverse skills and competencies in several disciplines spanning from data management to research and education networks to disaster risk management policies.

Workshop on OS, RDM and decision-making

Therefore, the report does not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the participating parties to the Brainstorming Workshop but just the hereby contribution of the three rapporteurs, namely:

- Mario Locati, Data Management Office Coordinator of the Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia ([INGV](#)) and Task Leader in the [Skills4EOSC](#) European project;
- Sara Di Giorgio, [GARR](#) External Relations and Communications Office, [Skills4EOSC](#) Coordinator;
- Giovanna Forlenza, Project Manager and Technologist at [INGV](#) and Service Management Team member of [ARISTOTLE-eENHSP](#).

Attachment

Agenda of the Workshop on Open Science, research data management and decision-making

Videoconference, 9th of April 2024

9:00 - 9:15 Welcome from the Organizers and introduction to the event
Massimo Cocco, Daniela Di Bucci

9:15 - 10:45 **Session 1: Framework definition**

The goal of this session is to present the current landscape on the topic from four different perspectives:

- i) pan-European initiatives fostering Open Science (OS);
- ii) Research infrastructures creating data;
- iii) European Civil Protection governing the EU context;
- iv) National Civil Protection using these data for decision- and policy-making.

Chairperson: Chiara Cardaci (ICPD)

9:15 - 9:30 The Pan-European framework of OS and RDM, EOSC
Volker Beckmann

9:30 - 9:45 Research Infrastructures: Open access to Data and RDM, EPOS
Massimo Cocco

9:45 - 10:00 Evidence-based Decision Making: pan-European context, DG-ECHO-KN
Gaetano Vivo

10:00 - 10:15 National Civil Protection Agency: open access and decision making, ICPD
Daniela Di Bucci

10:15 - 10:45 Questions/Answers

10:45 - 11:00 Break

11:00 - 13:00 **Session 2: Panel discussion on key aspects of open access to data, data management and decision-making**

Panelists: Alessandro Sola (DG-ECHO KN), Olimpia Imperiali (DG-ECHO ERCC), Alberto Michelini (Aristotle), Tom De Groeve (JRC), Giorgio Rossi (EOSC), Serge Scory (ENVRI)

Moderators: Emma Lazzeri (Skills4EOSC), Daniela Di Bucci (ICPD)

Tour de Table with Panelists (30 minutes)

Q/A from attendees (60 minutes)

Open discussion with attendees (30 minutes)

Rapporteurs: Mario Locati (INGV), Sara Di Giorgio (Skills4EOSC), Giovanna Forlenza (INGV, ARISTOTLE)